

Rieko Kodama, the First Lady of SEGA – Part Four

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In the previous entries, we discussed Kodama’s achievements in her early work, as well as those she attained as a producer and project lead at Sega. But what did she go on to do after the 1990s? By that time, the company had been weakened in terms of hardware sales, due to the efforts of competitors such as Nintendo and Sony. Weakened, but not defeated... and, in the 2000s, yet another major player entered the console wars: the American company Microsoft, with its Xbox in 2001.

By now, it should be clear why the epithet “the First Lady of Sega”, which forms part of the title of this series of articles dedicated to Rieko Kodama, is so fitting. It is based on titles such as the “First Lady of RPGs”, used to refer to her by outlets such as IGN and 1UP. And we have not yet finished telling you everything she worked on —nor what many consider to be her greatest contribution...

Keep reading to discover which new projects came to life with the help of Rieko Kodama in the 2000s!

The Turn of the Century for Kodama

Rieko Kodama never left Sega, and although the company ceased manufacturing home consoles some years ago —setting aside, for instance, the Mega Drive Mini models— it continued to develop major projects for its fans, despite the difficulties it began to face in the market in the late 1990s and early 2000s. Those who claim that Sega no longer produces video games tend to overlook the fact that it is behind franchises such as *Total War*, developed by The Creative Assembly.

We should not overlook, of course, titles such as the two legendary Shenmue games, released for the Dreamcast in 1999 and 2001 under the direction of Yū Suzuki.

Indeed, what is now widely regarded as Rieko Kodama's masterpiece was released precisely in the year 2000. We are referring to *Skies of Arcadia*, a title that rewards those who venture into it with a beautiful, detailed, and optimistic open world, as well as a strong sense of exploration inspired by adventure and travel literature. Although it was not a commercial hit —much like other Sega milestones such as the aforementioned Shenmue games— it became a cult classic, deeply appreciated by those who have played it.

From left to right, Cupil —floating—, Fina's artificial companion and the one responsible for her physical attacks, to the left and beneath Cupil; Aika —centre— and Vyse —right—.

The homage —intentional or not— to captain Harlock, created by Leiji Matsumoto, is more than evident, beginning with the fact that Harlock's ship is named *Arcadia*, while Vyse himself bears a certain physical resemblance to the character. To make matters even clearer, both stories revolve around a group of honourable pirates who fight against the tyranny of an oppressive regime. *Space Pirate Captain Harlock* —宇宙海賊キャプテンハーロック— brought the name *Arcadia* into space in 1976, whereas *Skies of Arcadia* carried it to the skies of a planet in the year 2000.

The game presents a variety of cultures and regions, all imbued with their own identity and a strong sense of credibility. Each dungeon differs from the last, the player can explore using their airship from the very beginning of the game, and there are even naval-style battles.

This work of art in the form of interactive entertainment was later released on the Nintendo GameCube —in its Director's Cut version, featuring additional content and graphical improvements, in 2002—, while a planned release for the PlayStation 2 was unfortunately cancelled after this version.

To place things into context, imagine a world in which continents float above the planet's surface and people travel between them using flying vehicles, very much in the style later seen in *Atlantis: The Lost Empire*, or earlier in the cinema of Hayao Miyazaki—with *Laputa: Castle in the Sky* (1986) being the most obvious reference—, as well as in the work of Jean Giraud—Moebius.

It also recalls the works of Jules Verne and Robert Louis Stevenson—particularly *Treasure Island*, published between 1881 and 1882—, where we encounter adventurous and exploratory characters, as well as pirates who may be noble at heart and in intention, such as the protagonists Vyse and Aika. These stand in contrast to other factions within the world, such as the Valuan Empire—with Galcian following the orders of his Empress to dominate the entire planet—, or the Black Pirates, opposed to the Blue Rogues to which the protagonists belong.

Another RPG franchise in which Kodama played a leading role is *7th Dragon*, whose first instalment was released for the Nintendo DS in 2009. The premise of the game is straightforward: the protagonists' world has been almost entirely overrun by dragons, and in order to reclaim it, all dragons must be exterminated. The series continued with titles such as *7th Dragon 2020* (released in 2011) and *7th Dragon 2020-II* (2013), both for the PlayStation Portable, and finally *7th Dragon III: Code VFD* for the Nintendo 3DS (2015).

Directed by Kazuya Niinō, one of the minds behind the *Etrian Odyssey* franchise, the series evokes the feel of classic dungeon crawlers: the exploration of vast and labyrinthine dungeons, puzzle-solving, demanding levels that require thorough exploration, and a level of resource management that is not merely recommended but essential. However, it also incorporates a narrative and artistic style that is less austere than that of other classic titles within the genre.

From Kodama, it inherits a strong emphasis on carefully crafted storytelling, something not particularly common in this type of game, which tends to focus more on grinding

—that is, gameplay sessions centred on highly repetitive tasks in which the player progresses slowly through numerous battles, often requiring long and intensive play sessions. These games also feature systems that allow for character customisation, enabling players to feel a sense of ownership over the characters and classes they choose. The first instalment focused on an epic struggle against dragons—to give you an idea of the scale, players had to defeat a total of 666 dragons in order to reach the final boss, the seventh dragon, from which the title takes its name—.

The following two entries, released on the PlayStation Portable, transport players to a futuristic Tokyo, featuring a distinctly 2000s anime-inspired aesthetic.

Nagamimi, a character from *7th Dragon III: Code VFD*, shown both in their original form—bottom, front—and in their human form—centre—; and Yaiba—top, back—. Nagamimi is a fixed character, whereas Yaiba is one of the selectable protagonist options—allowing the choice of a default name and class—, belonging to the samurai class.

By contrast, the Nintendo 3DS instalment blends multiple time periods and settings through the inclusion of time travel —prehistoric past, present, and future—, and benefited from a more ambitious production.

Final Years: Rieko Kodama as Mentor and Preservationist

The franchise most strongly imbued with her creative identity is *Phantasy Star*, which even expanded into the realm of open-world gaming with *Phantasy Star Online* —released in 2000 for the Dreamcast and later appearing on the Nintendo GameCube, Xbox, and PC—. The franchise continued with further instalments, although none involved Kodama directly, as in the case of *Phantasy Star Online*, which nevertheless offers an original storyline connected to earlier entries through numerous references and homages.

By this point, Kodama had effectively concluded her work on *Phantasy Star* —although many still associate her with the series as a whole— and had moved on to other projects. Not only did she help create new franchises alongside her colleagues at Sega, but she also played a key role in preserving classic video games through their re-release. This refers to the Sega Ages initiative —incidentally, a palindrome—, which began in 1996 on the Sega Saturn and continues to this day.

Illustrations by Rieko Kodama showing Alis with her mother, which appeared in the publication *Sega Developer Relay Essays*, 1991.

Sega Ages is the name given to the various collections and reissues of classic Sega titles. Rieko Kodama was actively involved in collections featuring series such as *Fantasy Zone* and *Phantasy Star* —notably in 2008—, and she also coordinated and supervised the re-release of other classic Sega games. For example, she took part in the Sega Ages 2500 initiative, which initially offered somewhat uneven 3D reinterpretations of Sega classics for the PlayStation 2, but saw a marked improvement in quality coinciding with her increasing involvement in the project.

A web-based version of the platform can be accessed online in Japanese, with an English version also available. There, users can find information and learn how to acquire various classic Sega titles —both developed and published by the company—, with details

on the platforms on which they are available.

A curious detail is that, in the Nintendo Switch collection released in 2018, Alex Kidd appears as the presenter for the different Sega titles included in the initiative, even jumping into his own game when *Alex Kidd in Miracle World* is selected. Within this collection, Rieko Kodama was among those responsible for producing versions of classic Sega titles such as *Sonic the Hedgehog* (2018), *Lightening Force: Quest for the Darkstar* (also 2018), and *Virtua Racing* (2019), for which she was the person who managed to locate the original source code.

Among the last roles she undertook before her passing were supervisory duties within Sega, opting to maintain a more discreet profile within the company.

She is credited in *Phantasy Star* on Switch alongside Yōsuke Okunari, the lead producer of this phase of Sega Ages, and also in *Alex Kidd in Miracle World DX* (2021) as a member of Sega's development team. This initiative to preserve classic games has been led since 2023 by Okunari himself, reflecting Sega's recognition of the need to safeguard its catalogue—which also includes properties from companies such as Atlus—, particularly after reaching a point at which it was no longer entirely clear which titles the company still held the rights to, due to the sheer volume of its catalogue and the loss of certain games over time.

A Delayed Recognition: Rieko Kodama within the Industry

Although Kodama's career in the video game industry spanned more than three decades, her name received the same treatment as that of many creatives and designers behind major gaming masterpieces—and not, in this case, because she was a woman—. A similar situation occurred with Kazuma Kaneko, whose designs are synonymous with the Shin Megami Tensei franchise—with recognition only arriving in the 2000s, after decades of contributing to the series, which he joined following *Digital Devil Story: Megami Tensei*—, including its Persona titles.

Another comparable case is that of Yokō Tarō, whose works are now regarded as cult classics and who is widely recognised today—despite having been largely unknown and overlooked at the time of the releases of the Drakengard series, *Magna Carta*, or the first *NieR*—. Nor should we forget what happened to Kenji Eno—a pioneer in narrative horror—, or Gunpei Yokoi—whose fame grew significantly after his death—; all of them figures worthy of future articles here.

Fortunately, Kodama did receive recognition during her lifetime, as did several of the aforementioned figures, and she was able to enjoy the appreciation of both the press and gaming enthusiasts. She read messages and comments from players, gave numerous interviews, and attended various events where attendees could meet the person behind the name and the work. Just three years before her passing, Rieko Kodama was honoured with the Game Developers Choice Awards Pioneer Award in 2019, in recognition of her outstanding contributions to Sega and to the video game industry as a whole.

From CoolJapan.es, we bid farewell to this great professional of the industry, whom we did not wish to leave without a proper tribute, and we leave you with a brief interview conducted on the occasion of the release of the Sega Mega Drive Mini in 2019—in Japanese, with Japanese and English subtitles—, which you can watch via the following link.

What is your favourite video game among those in which Rieko Kodama was involved?

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** Destructoid, Eurogamer, One Million Power, Moby Games, Sega Ages Online, Sega Retro | **Text by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]

- **Images sourced from:** Biblio, SMS Power, Sega Bits, IGN, Shmuplations, Dreamcast Magazine

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